

WAYS TO IMPROVE THE REGULATORY FRAMEWORK FOR HUMAN CAPITAL MANAGEMENT IN IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION

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Annotation: *The importance of efficient use of human resources is growing in today's modern market economy, where science is advanced, the digital economy is becoming more widespread, information technology is covering all areas, and competition is developing. In particular, today the task of improving the current regulatory documents on improving the structure and dynamics of human capital to improve the quality of education and their effective use in the reform of the education system is becoming increasingly important.*

Key words: *human capital, higher education system, regulatory documents, labor market, human resources, competition, market economy, intellectual potential.*

Human capital management is carried out through the search, selection, development, training, evaluation, certification, motivation, labor incentives, organizational development and career management as organizational measures aimed at meeting the needs of the organization for its own resources. After all, “we need to nurture a new generation of knowledgeable and qualified personnel who will emerge as enterprising reformers, think strategically. In order to raise the level of knowledge not only of young people, but also of all members of our society, first of all, we need knowledge and high spirituality. »¹⁰¹.

Indeed, human capital is not only the sum of knowledge, skills and abilities possessed by man, but it is: first, the accumulated stock of knowledge, skills and abilities. Second, it is such a reserve that it is spent on social processing by man in one or another environment and allows for an increase in labor productivity as well as production. Third, the purposeful use of the accumulated stock of knowledge, skills and abilities leads to an increase in the wage of the worker at high productivity of activity. Fourth, the increase in income motivates and motivates a person and accumulates a reserve of new knowledge and skills, which can be used effectively in the future.

In a market economy, the training of highly qualified specialists in countries will increase competition in the market of higher education services. Competition affects

¹⁰¹ Shavkat Mirziyoyev: “The path of democratic reforms is the only and most correct way for us». **FROM THE APPEAL of the President to the Senate and the Legislative Chamber of the Oliy Majlis.** 28.01.2020. [HTTP://PAXTAKOR29.UZ](http://PAXTAKOR29.UZ) > ..

the quality of training of highly qualified specialists. This, in turn, requires the continuous development of the general education system to train highly qualified competitive professionals and the transition to the concept of personal development of qualified professionals. According to the data, the demand for higher education in the world is growing, for example, in 2000 there were 97 million students, and by 2025 this figure could reach 262 million¹⁰².

Improving the quality of education and improving the effectiveness of training competitive personnel will be achieved through the improvement of current regulations on human capital management. Defining priorities for systemic reform of higher education in the Republic of Uzbekistan, raising the process of training highly qualified personnel with modern knowledge and high moral and ethical qualities to a qualitatively new level, modernization of higher education, development of social and economic sectors based on advanced educational technologies targeted.

In particular, it shows that in advanced developed countries such as Germany, Sweden, Scotland, the United States, there are models of development in which the labor market is interrelated with the market of higher education services. While the Swedish labor market model is based on stimulating supply and demand based on various developed programs, the Scottish labor market model examines the social services that occur between labor resources producers and consumers by the Scottish Qualifications Board.

The Scottish Government evaluates the qualifications department by scientifically studying the producers and consumer services of higher education services and, in collaboration with experts, develops the content and method of assessing professional qualifications in collaboration with employers.

The U.S. model develops different programs to regulate different higher education services and labor markets (Technical Preparation for a World-Class Work Force)¹⁰³. A "Tech Prep" consortium has been formed to implement this program. Its main purpose is to prepare vocational training and image of the workplace, as well as to develop new areas of professionalism. There are no laws regulating labor relations in the United States, but labor agreements are made with the employer and the union that are hiring. Public services have been established in the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, Germany, Finland, and Japan to provide employment. There are national banks of jobs in public service organizations, which are responsible for collecting data on jobs, occupational and psychological unemployment and disseminating the collected information on a computer basis. Employment bureaus use this information through a dedicated terminal.

¹⁰² Katsarova I. Higher education in the EU approaches, issues and trends. European Parliamentary Research Service. Members' Research Service March 2015 — PE 554. 169. p 3. <http://www.eprs.ep.parl.union.eu>

¹⁰³ Migranov L.I. Sovershenstvovanie mehanizma vzaimodeystviya rynka truda i rynka obrazovatelnyx uslug. Institute of State Management, Law and Innovative Technologies (IGUPIT) Internet-journal «SCIENCE» №1 2013. 4 c.

The main problem in the current context is that the relationship between higher education services and the labor markets is a non-compliance with the requirements of the law of supply and demand, the basic economic law of a market economy.

In order to ensure that higher education in our country does not lag behind world higher education, it requires the effective use of the positive experience of international higher education. It is also necessary to take into account the socio-economic characteristics of our country when applying their experience in our country.

In conclusion, in the current context of improving the quality of education, it is necessary to constantly diversify their activities in higher education institutions and improve management processes. At the same time, it determines the relevance of the assessment of human capital by employees of higher education institutions as an important economic resource.

It is directly related to investments in science and higher education as a key component in improving the quality of human capital. It is necessary to ensure the interconnected development of higher education services and labor markets and improve the system of regulatory documents. It is also necessary to further improve the skills and practical experience of students in the development of the education system in our country in accordance with the requirements of the labor market. Employment should be based on the experience of the United States, the United Kingdom, Australia, Canada, Germany, Finland and Japan.

It is expedient to develop public-private partnership in the country, to establish technoparks, to develop and gradually introduce a legal framework for training by qualified personnel in public and sectoral or employer enterprises.

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